

Appendix

Exercises based on movie scenes to be solved by the students.

1. *Movie: Fast & Furious 7 (2015). Scene cut: 1:14:17 to 1:15:10.*

In this scene, the main character lifts up the front part of a car using only his hands while another character places himself under the car. Is it possible for a man to lift a car in this way without any mechanical help?

Solution:

The car is a Lykan Hypersport, a supercar with a mass of 1380 kg (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lykan_HyperSport). However, when it is lifted in this scene, the rear wheels remain in contact with the floor, so it should be noted that the applied force is not equal to the total weight of car. In Fig. 12, we can see a representation of the problem.

Figure 12

The engine of this car is located in the rear position, so the centre of gravity must be near that position. Here, we suppose that the distance from the centre of gravity to the fulcrum is one-third of the length between the fulcrum and the point where the external force is applied.

The minimum force necessary to raise the car can be calculated considering that it is the force necessary to equilibrate the action of the weight. Actually, it should be more, but it is the only force that we can calculate without knowing the acceleration of the lifting.

So, to have rotational equilibrium, it must be verified that:

$$F * L = W * \frac{L}{3}$$

$$F = \frac{W}{3} = \frac{1380 \text{ kg} * 9.8 \text{ m/s}^2}{3} = \boxed{4508 \text{ N}}$$

This way of lifting a car is similar to deadlifting. In this sport, the world record is 500 kg (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Deadlift>), which requires a minimum force of 4900 N. Hence, the world's top deadlifters, with the appropriate equipment, could probably lift this car; however, we do not believe that the main character belongs to this population.

2. *Movie: Superman (1978). Scene cut: 2:10:10 to 2:12:15.*

In this scene, Superman flies very fast around the Earth in order to stop its rotation and make it spin the other way around. What is the force that must be applied to the Earth to stop its rotation in the way and within the timeframe that Superman does it?

Solution:

The Earth is rotating with an angular velocity ω_0 . To stop it, an angular acceleration α must be applied. This can be calculated by:

$$\alpha = \frac{-\omega_0}{t}$$

where t is the time to stop the rotation.

The angular acceleration must be provided by the moment of a force M , following the equation:

$$\vec{M} = I * \vec{\alpha}$$

where I is the moment of inertia. The moment of the force is calculated by the cross product between the distance with the rotation axis and the force. If the force is applied in the equator and tangentially to it, then the module of the moment of the force can be calculated from:

$$M = -R * F$$

where R is the radius of the Earth and F is the applied force. The negative sign comes from the fact that M must be opposite to the rotation to stop it. Therefore, combining all these equations, we have:

$$-R * F = I * \frac{-\omega_0}{t}$$

$$F = \frac{I * \omega_0}{R * t}$$

The values of the different parameters are:

$$I = \frac{2}{5} m * R^2 = 9.69 * 10^{37} \text{ kg m}^2.$$

Mass of the Earth $m = 5.972 * 10^{24} \text{ kg}$.

Radius of the Earth $R = 6.371 * 10^6 \text{ m}$.

$\omega_0 = 7.27 * 10^{-7} \text{ rad/s}$.

$t = 11 \text{ s}$.

Based on the above, $F = \boxed{10^{26} \text{ N}}$, which is incredibly high. Perhaps even too high for Superman.

3. *Movie: Star Wars Episode VII – The Force Awakens (2015). Scene cut: 1:35:18 to 1:36:20.*

The *Millennium Falcon* travels through the galaxy at the speed of light (as is stated in the film). Subsequently, it enters a planet's atmosphere and slows down to a drastically lower velocity (assumed to be around 200 km/hour). If it started to decrease its velocity when it was at a distance from the planet similar to the distance between the Moon and the Earth, what negative acceleration was applied to the starship?

Solution:

If the starship has a uniform acceleration, the distance travelled is:

$$d = v_0 * t + \frac{1}{2} a * t^2$$

where v_0 is the initial velocity (speed of light in vacuum), a is the acceleration and t is the time to traverse the distance.

The time can be calculated taking into account that the final velocity comes from:

$$v = v_0 + a * t$$

$$t = \frac{v - v_0}{a}$$

Combining both equations, we have:

$$a = \frac{v_0(v - v_0) + 0.5(v - v_0)^2}{d}$$

The values of the different parameters are:

$$v_0 = 3 * 10^8 \text{ m/s.}$$

$$v = 55.5 \text{ m/s.}$$

$$d = 3.844 * 10^8 \text{ m.}$$

Therefore, the negative acceleration is $\boxed{-1.17 * 10^8 \text{ m/s}^2}$, which should have killed all the people inside the starship.

4. *Movie: The League of Extraordinary Gentlemen (2003). Scene cut: 0:59:10 to 0:59:40.*

Allan Quatermain, with a mass of 70 kg, jumps out of a moving car that has an approximate velocity of 60 km/hour. When he lands, he is motionless, without any velocity. What is the force that must have applied to his legs to stop his movement in the horizontal direction if we consider that the time taken to slow down is 0.5 s?

Solution:

Here, we have to use the Second Newton's Law:

$$\vec{F} = m * \vec{a}$$

where m is the mass of Allan Quatermain and a is the acceleration. The force that Allan's legs are going to experience can be calculated from the fact that it is necessary to stop the horizontal velocity:

$$v = v_0 + a * t = 0$$

$$a = -v_0/t$$

So, we have:

$$F = \frac{-m * v_0}{t}$$

The values of the different parameters are:

$m = 70$ kg.

$t = 0.5$ s.

$v_0 = 60$ km/hour = 16.67 m/s.

Therefore, the force is 2338 N, which should certainly have resulted in Allan's legs breaking.

5. Movie: Indiana Jones and the Kingdom of the Crystal Skull (2008). Scene cut: 0:19:50 to 0:21:40.

Indiana Jones, with a mass of 85 kg, enters a refrigerator with a mass of 30 kg to shelter from a nuclear explosion. Shortly after the explosion, the refrigerator flies through the air, with Indiana inside, overtaking a car that has an approximate horizontal velocity of 80 km/h (22.22 m/s) and taking 14 s to complete the journey. What is the exit angle of

the refrigerator with the horizontal? What is the output velocity of the refrigerator? What is the maximum height that it reaches? What is the distance travelled?

Solution:

Figure 13.

Firstly, according to the scheme of Figure 13, the motion equations are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} a_x &= 0 & V_x &= V_{ox} & x &= x_0 + V_{ox} \cdot t \\ a_y &= -g & V_y &= V_{oy} - g \cdot t & y &= y_0 + V_{oy} \cdot t - \frac{1}{2}g \cdot t^2 \end{aligned}$$

By knowing that when the refrigerator is at the maximum height, V_y takes null value and at this point the time is half of what is necessary to complete the entire path, we can calculate V_{oy} :

$$\begin{aligned} V_y = V_{oy} - \frac{g \cdot t}{2} \rightarrow 0 = V_{oy} - \frac{g \cdot t}{2} \rightarrow V_{oy} &= \frac{g \cdot t}{2} = \frac{9.81 \cdot 14}{2} = 68.67 \text{ m/s} \\ &= 247.21 \text{ km/h} \end{aligned}$$

Now, with the initial vertical and horizontal velocity, we can calculate the exit angle and the initial velocity:

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{V_{oy}}{V_{ox}} \right) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{68.67}{22.22} \right) = 72.07^\circ$$

$$V_o = \frac{V_{oy}}{\sin(\alpha)} = \frac{68.67}{\sin(72.07^\circ)} = 72.18 \text{ m/s} = 259.83 \text{ km/h}$$

The maximum height reached by the refrigerator is obtained with the time that it takes to complete half the distance.

$$y_{\max} = y_0 + \frac{V_{oy} \cdot t}{2} - \frac{1}{2}g \left(\frac{t}{2} \right)^2 = 0 + \frac{68.67 \cdot 14}{2} - \frac{1}{2}9.81 \cdot \left(\frac{14}{2} \right)^2 = 240.35 \text{ m}$$

Finally, the maximum distance travelled is given by:

$$x_{\max} = x_0 + V_{ox} \cdot t = 0 + 22.22 \cdot 14 = \boxed{311.08 \text{ m}}$$

6. *Movie: Spiderman (2002). Scene cut: 1:37:20 to 1:38:40.*

The Green Goblin holds Mary Jane (58 kg) on a crane of considerable height. He throws her off the crane, but Spiderman (80 kg) jumps about three seconds after her and reaches her. Is this possible? After that, Spiderman releases Mary Jane due to an action of the Green Goblin. She falls for about 4 m until she manages to grab a railing. What velocity did Mary Jane have when she grabbed the railing?

Consider that the motion equations are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{y,MJ} &= g & V_{y,MJ} &= V_{oy,MJ} + g \cdot (t + 3) & y_{MJ} \\ & & &= y_{o,MJ} + V_{oy,MJ} \cdot (t + 3) + \frac{1}{2} g \cdot (t + 3)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_{y,Spidey} &= g & V_{y,Spidey} &= V_{oy,Spidey} + g \cdot t & y_{Spidey} \\ & & &= y_{o,Spidey} + V_{oy,Spidey} \cdot t + \frac{1}{2} g \cdot t^2 \end{aligned}$$

Solution:

Spiderman could never reach Mary Jane since the initial velocity of both individuals is null, Spiderman does not gain momentum when jumping to rescue her, and they have the same acceleration. Table 2 outlines this more clearly.

Table 2.

In order to answer the question of what velocity Mary Jane has when she grabs the railing, the following motion equations have to be considered:

$$a_{y,MJ} = g \quad V_{y,MJ} = V_{oy,MJ} + g \cdot t \quad y_{MJ} = y_{o,MJ} + V_{oy,MJ} \cdot t + \frac{1}{2} g \cdot t^2$$

Taking into account that, again, the initial velocity is zero and since she gains no momentum, we can calculate the fall time and the final velocity:

$$y_{MJ} = y_{o,MJ} + V_{oy,MJ} \cdot t + \frac{1}{2}g \cdot t^2 \rightarrow 4 = 0 + 0 \cdot t + \frac{1}{2}9.81 \cdot t^2 \rightarrow t = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot 4}{9.81}}$$

$$= 0.90 \text{ s}$$

$V_{y,MJ} = V_{oy,MJ} + g \cdot t = 0 + 9.81 \cdot 0.90 = 8.83 \text{ m/s} = \boxed{31.79 \text{ km/h}}$, which should certainly have resulted in Mary Jane's arms breaking.

7. *Movie: Species 2 (1998). Scene cut: 0:02:14 to 0:03:25.*

The scene shows the crew members of a spaceship orbiting Mars having a conversation in real time — with a lag of merely a few seconds — with people at the base in Houston, on Earth. Considering that Mars is located at an average distance from our planet of, approximately, 225 millions of kilometres, how much time should the movie scene have actually taken if the laws of physics had been respected? Why?

Note that, in the scene, the crew members from the spaceship orbiting Mars address Houston on Earth twice, with the corresponding answers from the latter.

Solution:

The communications between the spaceship orbiting Mars and the base on Earth are established through electromagnetic waves, which travels at the speed of light ($3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$).

Hence, the time needed to establish one-way communication should be:

$$t = \frac{\text{distance}}{\text{speed}} = \frac{225 \cdot 10^9}{3 \cdot 10^8} = 750 \text{ seconds} = 12.5 \text{ minutes}$$

Therefore, according the laws of physics and taking into account that the communication of the scene consists of two round trips undertaken by electromagnetic waves, the scene should have lasted: $4 \cdot 12.5 = \boxed{50 \text{ minutes}}$.

Figure 12. Scheme of the problem to be solved in exercise 1.

Figure 13. Scheme of the problem to be solved in exercise 5.

Table 2. Velocities and distances traversed by Mary Jane and Spiderman in exercise 6.

<i>Character</i>	<i>Time (s)</i>	V_y (m/s)	Y (m)
Mary Jane	0.25	31.88	51.81
Spiderman		2.45	0.31
Mary Jane	0.5	34.34	60.09
Spiderman		4.91	1.23
Mary Jane	1	39.24	78.48
Spiderman		9.81	4.905

Figure captions

Figure 12. Scheme of the problem to be solved in exercise 1.

Figure 13. Scheme of the problem to be solved in exercise 5.